

The Unjournal

Evaluation 1 of "Forecasting Existential Risks: Evidence from a Long-Run Forecasting Tournament", Applied Stream

Evaluator 1

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ABSTRACT

[Here we will include the ~75 word, 400 character summary that we will request evaluators to provide. Otherwise, we will use an LLM-generated summary (and note this is the case).]

[Here, we offer a template for hosting Unjournal evaluations in PubPub, version 6. This template can also be used for sharing with authors (as a draft), for their response, before the full package is released.]

[To proceed...¹]

Summary Measures

We asked evaluators to give some overall assessments, in addition to ratings across a range of criteria. See the [evaluation summary “metrics”](#) [link evaluation summary draft, view mode, ‘metrics’ header] for a more detailed breakdown of this. See these ratings in the context of all Unjournal ratings, with some analysis, in our [data presentation here](#).²

<i>REPLACE WITH ACTUAL RATINGS HERE</i>	Rating	90% Credible Interval
Overall assessment	55/100	45 - 63
Journal rank tier, normative rating	3.5/5	2.6 - 4.8

Overall assessment: We asked evaluators to rank this paper “heuristically” as a percentile “relative to all serious research in the same area that you have encountered in the last three years.” We requested they “consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice.”

Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5): “On a ‘scale of journals’, what ‘quality of journal’ should this be published in? (See ranking tiers discussed [here](#))” Note: 0= lowest/none, 5= highest/best”.

See [here](#) for the full evaluator guidelines, including further explanation of the requested ratings.

Written report**Footnotes**

1. Create a new ‘pub’, import evaluator’s content, copy in the material below, filling in as necessary, and checking/adjusting to maintain the desired formatting. ‘Pub settings’ will need adjusting. Pub settings will also need to be configured. See our internal Coda documentation. [↪](#)

2. Note: if you are reading this before, or soon after this has been publicly released, the ratings from this paper may not yet have been incorporated into that data presentation. [↵](#)